

Renewable Energy Integration in the DRC: A Strategic Modelling Study

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Executive Summary

The objective of our study was to model the integration of renewable energy into the electricity system in the DRC using OSeMOYS tool. In order to increase energy supply, we propose an energy mix that is appropriate for the Congolese situation. To achieve this, we developed three scenarios, including the least-cost scenario (LC), the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario and the renewable energy technologies uptake (RE) scenario. The first scenario considers the existing energy mix without any constraints. The second scenario is based on the government's policy of investment in the electricity sector. The third scenario requires non-investment in non-renewable energy sources. In terms of the results obtained, the least-cost scenario (LC) is less expensive than the other two scenarios, while the renewable energy scenario (RE) is more expensive than the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. However, the difference between the three scenarios is not significant. The LC scenario has invested in both non-renewable and renewable sources. The scenario is identical to BAU, with the exception of the difference in installed capacity. Despite the slightly lower cost than the other scenarios, RE appears to be the most optimal scenario for the DRC, taking into account the DRC's commitment to climate change mitigation. It is therefore recommended that political decision-makers and policymakers facilitate increased investments in the renewable energy sector and install solar and hydroelectric power stations through mini-grid and off-grid systems to increase the rate of access to electricity.

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1. Introduction

The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) possesses vast energy potential, comprising abundant hydrological and solar resources, extensive tropical forests covering 67% of its land area, and the availability of forestry and agricultural waste along with methane reserves, notably the 50 Gm³ reserve in Lake Kivu. Irradiance levels range between 3.5 and 5.5 kWh/day/m², with even higher levels in southern regions, complemented by the presence of cobalt, a crucial mineral for modern rechargeable batteries. Despite this rich resource base, less than 19% of the population has access to electricity. However, 19%, with rural areas accounting for less than 1% and urban areas accounting for approximately 35% (Bank et al., 2019).

Regarding electricity production, renewable energy sources dominate the Congolese energy mix, with hydropower contributing 97% with the National Utility Company (SNEL) as the primary supplier (Matters and ESRG, 2020). However, due to technical issues, lack of maintenance, and inadequate funding, only about 70% of the installed production capacity of approximately 2,8 GW is produced (Matters and ESRG, 2020). Furthermore, the country has an estimated hydropower potential of 100 GW, from which the Congo River, located in the *Kongo Central* province, can produce almost half of its total power potential (Kusakana, 2016).

This disparity underscores a structural lack of investment capacity across various energy technologies which leads to the need to establish energy planning. To address this challenge, it becomes imperative to model the optimal energy mix to meet the increasing demand for electricity within the DRC. OSeMOSYS emerges as a valuable tool for achieving this goal, enabling stakeholders to strategize and plan for a more sustainable and inclusive energy future for the country.

This study seeks to determine the optimal energy mix to meet the growing demand for electricity in the DRC until 2063.

2. Methodology

OSeMOSYS is a tool used for modeling global energy trends, from big regions down to local areas. It helps predict the best pathways to minimize costs and meet energy needs (M. Howells, et al. 2011). In the case of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), our objective is to use OSeMOSYS to study its energy system over an extended period. The study will begin with basic data sets, such as the 'Starter Kit' (Carla Cannone, M. Howells, et al. 2021), in addition to data from authoritative sources, including the International Energy Agency (IEA), the International

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Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), the African Energy Commission (AFREC), governmental agencies affiliated with the Ministry of Electricity and Hydraulic Resources, and openly accessible documents. To ensure the accuracy of our model, we will calibrate the data in the data starter kit using data from documents that reflect the current context of the DRC. Various scenarios will be examined to assess the various routes towards sustainable energy in the DRC.

- **Least-cost scenario (LC):** This scenario identifies the most cost-effective energy mix to meet future electricity demand in the DRC, considering all available energy technologies. In addition to the existing hydropower, geothermal, and solar PV resources, the DRC has the potential to develop further gas, wind, coal, and biomass resources. The optimal combination is evaluated to minimise electricity generation costs.
- **Business-as-Usual scenario (BAU):** The BAU scenario represents the current state of affairs in the energy sector. This scenario represents the current state of the energy system in the DRC, which is heavily reliant on hydropower (97% of capacity), with the remainder derived from geothermal, light fuel oil, and solar PV. The objective is to achieve 30% access to electricity for the population by 2030. Consequently, a total investment of 3.28222 GW is required in the power sector. Of this total, 80% is allocated to solar power. Furthermore, 11% of the total investment is earmarked for hydropower plants. Similarly, 0.54 GW of coal and 0.007 GW of biomass were invested in the same sector.
- **Renewable energy technologies uptake (RE):** This scenario examines the exclusive adoption of renewable energy technologies in the DRC, with a particular focus on hydropower, solar PV, wind, and biomass. The scenario evaluates the feasibility and impact of a renewable-only strategy, to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and enhance energy security. In this scenario, no further investments are made in coal, natural gas, or fuel after 2035. Existing power plants in these areas will continue producing electricity until they phase out.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Power Generation

As shown in Figure 1, power generation across all scenarios is almost the same in the early years, specifically in 2030. During this time, both the BAU and RE scenarios present the same energy mix, predominantly composed of coal power plants and hydropower plants. In contrast, the LC scenario includes an additional power plant, an oil-fired gas turbine producing 5 PJ, with solar PV contributing a very small proportion of 0.2 PJ. In both the BAU and RE scenarios, there is a combined power generation of roughly 11 PJ from solar PV utility and Solar PV (with distributed storage).

As the years progress, the production from oil-fired gas turbines increases significantly in all scenarios, reaching 68 PJ by 2040 and continuing this trend into 2050. However, by 2060, generation will increase only in the BAU and LC scenarios, while in the RE scenario, this generation will be replaced by Solar PV. This is because the BAU and LC scenarios do not impose constraints on power generation from oil-fired gas turbines in later years. When these plants reach the end of their life, new power plants of the same type are automatically invested in. In contrast, in the RE scenario, when fossil fuel power plants reach the end of their life, they are replaced by renewable energy technologies. The country is projected to achieve complete integration of renewable energy by 2070. Both the LC and BAU scenarios will feature an energy mix predominantly composed of renewable energy technologies, representing more than 70%.

Despite a particular emphasis on large hydropower plants in the DRC, it is evident that this solution will not meet the long-term electricity demand. The demand will exceed the generation capacity of hydropower alone. Therefore, the government is focusing on other technologies, particularly small solar power plants in rural areas (Power Africa, 2019, ANSER, 2023) However, this approach will not address the pressing and increasing electricity demand in the long run. Over the years, renewable energy technologies will play a significant role, but they will not be limited to hydropower plants connected to the grid. Solar, wind energy and off-grid hydropower plants must also be considered from 2060 onwards. A high share of gas power plants is also noted and suggested as a future investment. This will depend on current policy, which does not specify restrictions on investing in gas power

plants, especially given the significant reserves in Lake Kivu in the eastern region of the country.

Figure 1. Power generation 2020-2063 by technology.

3.2 Installed capacity of the power sector

Figure 2 shows installed capacity in the power sector. What stands out is that the installed capacity for all scenarios is the same in 2020. Starting in 2025, the installed capacity in the BAU and RE scenarios will be greater than in the LC scenario due to new investments in renewable energy technologies, which have lower capacity factors. By 2040, there will be an increase in the installed capacity of oil-fired gas turbines across all scenarios, as well as an increase in solar PV, bringing the installed capacity in the LC scenario to equal that of BAU. Meanwhile, RE will maintain a higher installed capacity, explained by the phasing out of fossil-fuel technologies and their replacement by renewable energy technologies with lower capacity factors. Over the years, the installed capacity of the energy mix in the RE scenario will significantly increase compared to the BAU and LC scenarios. By 2063, the installed capacity in the RE scenario will be 88 GW, while in the BAU and LC scenarios, it will be respectively 52 GW and 55 GW, with a proportion of gas power plants and oil-fired gas turbines that have a higher capacity factor.

If the country aims to increase investment in renewable energy technologies, it is evident that a substantial number of power plants will need to be constructed to address the intermittent nature of energy sources including solar PV and wind power. This will depend on the size of

the projects. Currently, the transmission lines are defective and do not allow the entire population to have access to electricity (Power Africa, 2019). Extending the existing grid is very costly, and those funds could be better used to invest in other electrification solutions. A common suggestion is to implement mini-grid and off-grid solutions to accelerate the electrification of the DRC (ACERD, 2021).

On the other hand, all scenarios still involve a high share of renewable energy technologies compared to other technologies, but this highlights how the high capacity factors of oil-fired gas turbines and gas power plants influence the installed capacity of the energy mix each year.

Figure 2. Installed capacity 2020-2063 by technology.

3.3 Total emissions

All scenarios follow the same increasing pattern in total emissions from 2020 until 2057, rising from 456 MtCO₂e in 2020 to 711 MtCO₂e in the BAU and LC scenarios, and to 654 MtCO₂e in the RE scenario. In 2058, there is a significant decrease in emissions for the RE scenario, dropping from 654 MtCO₂e in 2057 to 411 MtCO₂e in 2058. In the other scenarios, there is a progressive decrease, first from 711 MtCO₂e in 2057 to 633 MtCO₂e in 2058, and then to 411 MtCO₂ in 2059. The model does not take into account only electricity sector but also other energy sources that why all scenarios follow the same pattern over the years.

Figure 3. Annual GHG emissions 2020-2063

3.4 Total cost for each scenario

The total discounted cost encompasses the capital, fixed, and variable costs associated with the evolution of the energy system. As illustrated in Figure 4, the total costs for the BAU, RE, and LC scenarios are estimated at US\$291.3 billion, US\$292.9 billion, and US\$290.9 billion respectively. The Renewable Energy Uptake scenario requires a higher investment than the other scenarios, but the difference is not significant. This may be because renewable energy technologies are dominant in all scenarios. The dominance of renewable energy technologies is due to the current energy mix being dominated by hydropower plants. Therefore, the DRC has a clear path in deciding which technology to invest in and does not face the same energy transition challenges as other countries.

The main issue for the DRC is to increase the electrification rate so that reliance on bioenergy for cooking may significantly decrease. Although renewable energy technologies represent 97% of electricity production, they account for less than 5% of the total energy mix in the country (IRENA,2023).

Figure 4. Total discounted system cost 2020-2063

Since the study focuses only on power generation, the emissions of CO₂ from other energy sources are not included, making it difficult to evaluate the implications of different scenarios and energy mixes comprehensively. This study concentrated solely on the electricity sector. However, the DRC faces challenges not only in the power sector but also in cooking and transport, which require particular attention. These areas present future avenues for research to contribute to the development of the Congolese energy sector holistically and, consequently, enhance the country's economy.

4. Conclusion

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is endowed with abundant natural resources, positioning it as a potential driver for the development of the African continent. However, the lack of electricity severely hinders the country's economic development and affects the population's quality of life in areas such as education, healthcare, lighting, clean cooking etc. To address these challenges, creating a conducive business climate to attract investment in the energy sector is crucial. Diversifying the energy mix, currently dominated by hydropower, is essential for a reliable electricity supply.

Modelling results indicate that all three scenarios present similar total discounted costs. Nonetheless, given the DRC's commitment to mitigating climate change, the Renewable Energy Uptake (RE) scenario, although the most expensive, emerges as the optimal solution. This

scenario envisions an energy mix predominantly composed of renewable technologies by 2063, with minimal reliance on coal and gas power plants. Off-grid hydropower, medium hydropower, biomass, and solar PV with storage dominate the renewable energy share in the RE scenario.

It is important to note that existing transmission lines are defective due to inadequate maintenance and investment. Consequently, there is a growing advocacy for mini-grid and off-grid solutions to enhance electrification rates. Our model indicates that off-grid hydropower is the preferred solution in the RE scenario, accounting for a significant proportion compared to other hydropower plants considered.

The Congolese government should focus on grid-connected solutions and small solar projects and prioritise mini-grid and off-grid solutions. While the current grid conditions will only electrify approximately 15% of the population, mini-grid and off-grid solutions offer a broader reach, potentially extending electricity access to a larger segment of the Congolese population.

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